

***GIBBERELLIN 3-OXIDASE* genes regulate height and grain size in bread wheat**

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Supplementary Figures S1 to S10:

Supplementary Figure S1: Effect of EMS-induced mutations in *GA3OX2*, *GA3OX3* and *GAI1OX1* genes in wheat.

Supplementary Figure S2: Inflorescence development in *ga3ox2* mutants.

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Supplementary Figure S9: Geographic distribution of *GA3OX3-B1-GA1OX1-B1* haplotypes.

Supplementary Figure S10: Grain expression levels of *GA3OX3-B1* and *GA1OX1-B1* in 30 wheat accessions.

Supplementary Figure S1: Effect of selected EMS-induced mutations in *GA3OX2*, *GA3OX3* and *GA1OX1* genes in wheat. **(A)** Effect of EMS-mutations in *GA3OX2* and *GA3OX3* lines. * indicates premature stop codon. The natural, non-functional *ga3ox3-d1* allele in ‘Cadenza’ is shown. **(B)** Position of splice-site mutation in *GA1OX1-B1* in line Cadenza 1684.

Supplementary Figure S2: Representative images of inflorescence development in wildtype 'Cadenza' and *ga3ox2* development using a light microscope.

Supplementary Figure S3: Height of wild-type, single and double *ga3ox2* mutants in glasshouse conditions. Upper-case letters indicate a wild-type allele for that homoeologue and lower case indicate a loss-of-function allele (Table 1). Mutant genotypes were compared by two-tailed Student's t-tests with the wild-type genotype AABBDd. * $P < 0.05$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Supplementary Figure S4: Physical location of *GA3OX3* and *GA1OX1-B1* genes on homoeologous group 2 chromosomes in the landrace ‘Chinese Spring’ IWGSC RefSeq v1 genome assembly. Gene positions are drawn to scale, and homologous genes are linked by lines determined using the Triticeae Gene Tribe microhomology tool (Chen, Song et al. 2020). On chromosome 2B, *GA1OX1-B1* and *GA3OX3-B1* are separated by 5,087 bp in the ‘Chinese Spring’ genome and 3,618 bp in the ‘Cadenza’ genome.

Supplementary Figure S5: Detection of GA₅₄ in developing grain of different wheat species. Mass chromatograms for m/z 506, the molecular ion for GA₅₄ methyl ester trimethylsilyl ether, are shown from selected ion monitoring by GC-MS of extracts of developing grain or spikelets.

Supplementary Figure S6: Geometric mean height (cm) of GA3OX3 and GA1OX1 wildtypes and mutants in glasshouse conditions. Bars represent 95% confidence intervals. *GA3OX3* vs. *ga3ox3*: $F_{1,59} = 13.14$, $P < 0.001$; *GA1OX1* vs. *ga1ox1*: $F_{1,59} = 2.92$, $P = 0.093$.

Supplementary Figure S7: Pairwise amino acid identity between GA3OX3, GA3OX2 and GA1OX1 proteins in wheat. *GA3OX3-D1* does not encode a full-length protein and was excluded from the analysis.

Supplementary Figure S8: Haplotypic variation in *GA3OX2* genes within the Watkins collection of wheat landraces. Haplotypes with fewer than 10 accessions were filtered from the analysis.

Supplementary Figure S9: Distribution of *GA3OX3-B1-GAI1OX1-B1* allele types in different global regions ($N = 1017$).

Supplementary Figure S10: Expression levels of *GA3OX3* and *GA1OX1* in 30 wheat accessions from grains at 14 DPA. Haplotypes are indicated from accessions that were assayed. Grain expression data from Nirmal *et al.* 2017.

